

LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ATTRIBUTES TOWARDS EDUCATION PROGRESSION DRIVEN-ERA OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of leadership styles and the extent of attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public secondary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of leadership styles was extensive while the extent of attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for leadership styles have a strong positive relationship to the attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of leadership styles on attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators: Behavior, Transformational, and Transactional. It was recommended that potential school administrators must have proper training on the functions or roles of school administrators before taking the position of school administrators. It is also recommended that teachers must also be aware of the functions of school administrators to fully understand and appreciate the tasks and achievements of their leaders.

KEY WORDS

1. Leadership styles.
2. attributes towards education .
3. progression-driven era.

1. Introduction

Leadership, they say is a universal phenomenon and has been the subject of continuous research. The definitions of leadership are complex, elusive, and somewhat contradictory. Others believe that people-oriented leaders are the most effective, however, some believe that the result of every leader's action determines his success. Relating to school leadership, the success of a school may be equated to the quality of leadership of its school administrator. The school administrator is a principal, a school head, or a teacher in charge who is designated to run a school. Though he may have different titles, he is regarded as the school leader. He makes decisions on behalf of the school with the help of teachers, learners, parents, and other

stakeholders. But among all of those who help him, he is the one in command of all the activities and carries all the responsibilities of a certain school. However, as a leader, he always faces different challenges to achieve the goals of the institution he serves. He also faces different problems, whether these problems come from the teachers, learners, community, or other stakeholders. In addition, he is knowledgeable of the different theories on how to handle conflicts in behavior and leadership. He is assumed to possess skills in dealing with the diverse attitudes of learners, teachers, and stakeholders. He integrates knowledge with experience to be able to effectively deal with the problems that may arise as he leads his respective school. Also, as a school administrator, he may possess some of the skills that are necessary for effective leadership, but that is not enough. He should also be better in what he does; he has to expand his knowledge on effective leadership through the provision of administrative services. Formulates a policy framework for the operationalization of the administrative services in the Department. From the global perspective, effective leadership is necessary for the advancement of teachers as well as society. In the technological advancement of the 21st century, there are many challenges to compete including worldwide teachers' networks which demand a great educational leader for educational institutions. There are three main aspects of a principal's leadership in dealing with educational and cultural reforms such as increasing participation, transferring vision, and producing change. The effectiveness of leaders in the educational sector is valued by their competencies to contribute to improving the quality of education in the era of technological advancement (Abbas, et. al., 2020). The school administrator is also responsible for supporting the teachers in their teaching practices. Principals have a critical role to play in achieving the institution's goals and objectives. Among these responsibilities, principals must give genuine and effective leadership, resulting in improved professional presentation among teachers. The school administrator is responsible for giving highly valued visions that are focused on their day-to-day methods and that serve to foster a good culture that is supportive of exceptional teacher performance (Saleem, et. al., 2020). Similarly in the Philippines, the school administration carries the major burden of providing leadership if the school is no move forward. As a leader, the school administrator is the sort of a person who can motivate teachers to achieve tasks and maintain team unity throughout the process. Whatever style of leadership he may display is a matter of strategy and personality. School administrators have the power to influence the teacher morale in their school by the actions or daily practices they exhibit. Administrators are aware and conscious that teachers' high morale is a means of achieving better efficiency. The study of leadership styles takes into consideration what a leader does, says and how he acts (Reyes, 2019). According to Gelison (2016), school administrators hold a crucial position in the organization for the quality of leadership which greatly influences the quality of the school environment. The way school administrators lead their teachers depends on the leadership styles they adopt and the human behavior of their subordinates. School administration is somewhat of a metamorphosis. This is due to different programs initiated by the Department of Education such as the School Management system which empowers every school administrator to decide on specific matters concerning the school. This requires school administrators to possess knowledge, skills, and attitudes that differentiate them from their subordinates. The leadership styles, attributes, and functions of a school administrator and how he works to attain the goals, mission, and vision of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. The leadership styles manifested, attributes pos-

sessed, and functions complied by school administrators to be effective school leaders in this progression-driven era of education. Since, the school administrator is a leader, questions may arise on the qualities/attributes that set him apart from the other teachers who may also do the job. Republic Act 9155 which is also known

as Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 defines School Head as a person responsible for the administrative and instructional supervision of the school or cluster of schools. According to the law (RA 9155), the school head shall have authority, accountability, and responsibility.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction to this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument, and the data gathering procedures. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing the correlational method. According to Godines (2021), the descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Lazaga (2022) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses the leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since it determines leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in twelve (12) schools of Cluster, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120 selected teachers from Maa District, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years

of teaching experience in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something about the leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. Random sampling techniques were employed in this study. However, Carmen Integrated School and Valencia Integrated School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached through land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used an adapted questionnaire on characteristics of school administrators which was patterned and adapted by the researcher from the Great Man Theory by Carlye (1911) as cited by Jamon (2017). This suggests that the capacity to lead is inborn. This theory can be summarized in the phrase, “Great leaders are born, not made.” The notion of “Great Man” was used since during that time, leadership was thought of primarily as a male quality, especially in terms of military

leadership. This was also supported by the Trait Theory by Allport (1938) as cited by Cherry (2016). This theory focuses on identifying different personality traits and characteristics traits and characteristics that are linked to successful leadership. across a variety of situations. Some beliefs of the trait theory of leadership are certain traits produce certain patterns of behavior, these patterns are consistent across different situations, and people are born with leadership traits. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. The validity of the instrument was ensured through expert opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted by calculating the value of Cronbach's Alpha with the obtained value of 0.743. The questionnaire was

divided into two (2) parts, leadership styles and attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. Hence, Cronbach's value of the construct had met the minimum reliability of 0.784, which means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of the instrument's face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items leadership styles with the following behavioral, transformational, and transactional. Part 2 pertained to the attributes of an education progression-driven era with the dimensions, namely: knowledge, skill, and attitude. The perceptions of the respondents among the Cluster VI teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Leadership styles are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Leadership styles are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Leadership styles are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Leadership styles are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Leadership styles are not evident.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Attributes towards education progression era show a very high level.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Attributes towards education progression era show a high level.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Attributes towards education progression era show a moderate level.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Attributes towards education progression era show a low level.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Attributes towards education progression era show a very low level.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure—*

1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via Google Forms and through the email addresses of the school administrators and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent back through the researcher's email address or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2023. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who will be missed answering the questionnaire, a video call, via messenger, viber, zoom, or goggle meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean. It was used to determine the level of leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the significant components of leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was used to determine the significance of leadership styles' influence attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of leadership styles in terms of behavior, transformational, and transactional; the extent of attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in knowledge, skills, and attitudes; and which factors of leadership styles significantly influence the attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Leadership Styles of Public Secondary Schools Administrators. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of leadership style of public secondary school teachers. The indicator with highest mean is self-behavior with a mean of (3.98), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by

transformational has a mean of (3.61) also identified as extensive. Lastly, transactional has the lowest mean of (3.57) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.70) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the leadership styles of public secondary schools was extensive as perceived by the administrators.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Leadership Styles of Public Secondary Schools Administrators

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Behavior	3.93	Extensive
2	Transformational	3.61	Extensive
3	Transactional	3.57	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.70	Extensive

It can be gathered from the table that behavior and transformational were extensive. transactional was the least among the indicators of the leadership style of public secondary school administrators. Chin (2015) explains that leadership in the context of the American academic environment is a process of social influence through which an individual can enlist the aid and support of others in the attainment of common as well as ethical tasks. Northouse (2018) and Wu, et. al., (2020) highlight that leadership is a prominent power relationship in which one party (leader) promotes movements or changes in others (followers). Executives, school administrators, and staff are dedicated to their work and believe they have a stake in the organization. People at all levels feel more involved when

they have a say in choices that affect them and when their job is closely linked to the organization’s goals. Furthermore, effective leadership is required for the progress of both teachers and society. There are many hurdles to compete in the technology growth of the 21st century, including worldwide teacher networks, which necessitate a strong educational leader for educational institutions. A school administrator’s leadership in dealing with educational and cultural changes consists of three major aspects: boosting engagement, conveying vision, and generating change. The efficacy of educational leaders is measured by their ability to contribute to the improvement of educational quality in an era of technological growth (Abbas, et. al., 2020).

Summary on the Extent of Attributes Towards Education Progression-Driven Era Public Secondary Schools Administrators. Presented in table 2 shows the summary extent of attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. The indicator with the highest mean is

knowledge with a mean of (3.97), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by attitudes has a mean of (3.85) identified as extensive. Lastly, skills have the lowest mean of (3.82) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.88) or extensive, therefore, the summary extent of attributes towards education progression-

driven era of public secondary school was extensive as perceived by the administrators. This means that school administrators had positive attitudes towards education progression-driven in their employment in education. Addition-

ally, via worthwhile gains like improved quality and a reduction in learning time and effort in schools, the learners' knowledge of the relevance of tools would be guaranteed.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Attributes Towards Educational Progression-Driven Era Public Secondary Schools Administrators

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Knowledge	3.97	Extensive
2	Skills	3.82	Extensive
3	Attitudes	3.85	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.88	Extensive

It can be garnered from the table that knowledge, attitudes, and skills were extensively demonstrated by public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. In leadership, intelligence plays a vital role. Intelligent leaders are most likely to be successful in terms of decision-making and innovation because they can think critically. Intelligence may be born or nurtured. It can be gained from reading, education, and experience. In the case of school administrators, they most likely gained their intelligence from different mediums, but what is more important is that they use their intelligence in righteous ways. Leaders who share their vision with subordinates motivate subordinates to achieve the vision of the leaders, competence is earned through experience, taking responsibility is standing firm for the decisions made, and taking risk is someone's courage to gamble for something that he thinks is correct or righteous, and being resourceful is finding ways to address problems. However, teachers' perceptions are different from the school administrators. Teachers believe that school administrators merely possess the leadership skills. It is therefore fair enough to say that the self-evaluation of school administrators

on their skills is not in parallel with their teachers' perception. School administrators are unanimous that they well-possessed honesty and transparency, independence, passion, respect, and commitment which are for the researcher the most important attitudes that school leaders must possess. Being honest and transparent can gain the respect of subordinates; having independence can make school administrators free from political forces that would try to sway their decision-making; having passion makes the job of being a school administrator not a job but a calling; being respectable is gaining the respect of others without even asking for it; and, being committed to the job is someone's dedication to the job and willingness to take responsibility to his actions and decisions. Significant Relationship Between the Leadership Styles and Attributes Towards Education Progression-Driven Era of Public Secondary School Administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis of the significant relationship between the leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The overall p-value is equal

to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.765. This means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hy-

pothesis. The analysis further implies that an increasing manifestation of leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to an increased manifestation of their attributes towards the education progression-driven era.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Leadership Styles and Attributes Towards Education Progression-Driven Era of Public Secondary School Administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Leadership Styles	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Behavior	0.705	0.000	Reject
Transformational	0.584	0.000	Reject
Transactional	0.428	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.765	0.000	Reject

Particularly, the analysis in Table 9 highlighted also of the association between each indicator of the leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City, and their attributes towards an education progression-driven era. Based on the said analysis, the Behavior indicator of leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.705. This result implies that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the behavior of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City as an indicator of their leadership styles and their attributes towards an education progression-driven era. This was followed by the Transformational indicator of leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators with a p-value of 0.000 and -r-value of 0.584. This result implies that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the behavior of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City as an indicator of their leadership styles and their attributes towards an education progression-driven era. Ranked last is the Trans-

actional indicator of leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators with a p-value of 0.000 and -r-value of 0.428. Still, this result implies that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the behavior of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City as an indicator of their leadership styles and their attributes towards an education progression-driven era.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Leadership Styles on the Attributes Towards Education Progression-Driven Era of Public Secondary School Administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis on the significant influence of leadership styles on the attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and an F-value equal to 67.9000 which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the leadership styles have a significant influence on the attributes of the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI,

Division of Davao City. This further implies that the regression statistical treatment used in the analysis of the study is useful which means that there is validity in the interpretation of the assumption of the said influences. Relatively, the regression analysis as presented in the same table shows that all of the indicators of leadership styles significantly influenced the attributes towards the education progression-driven era

of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Therefore, the established null hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of leadership styles that significantly influence the attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City is rejected.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Leadership Styles on the Attributes Towards Education Progression-Driven Era of Public Secondary School Administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Leadership Styles	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho	
Constant	.660	.243	2.712	.000		
Behavior	.450	.048	.560	9.323	.000	Reject
Transformational	.272	.058	.316	4.695	.080	Reject
Transactional	.133	.063	.136	2.100	.038	Reject

Note: R = 0.798, R² = 0.637, F-Value = 67.900, p-value = .000

Particularly, these leadership styles indicators of public secondary school heads in accordance to their t-value were the Behavior indicator which received a t-value equal to 9.323 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Transformational indicator which received a t-value equal to 4.695 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Transactional indicator which received a t-value equal to 6.151 and a p-value equal to 0.000, and the Directive indicator which received a t-value equal to 2.100 and a p-value equal to 0.038. Moreover, the regression analysis results show an R-squared (R²) value of 0.637, indicating that 63.70 percent of the variation in the attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City, can be attributed to their leadership styles. An R² value of this magnitude is considered strong in social science research, providing a compelling case for the

significant influence of leadership styles on the attributes of the education progression-driven era of public secondary school heads. This high R² value demonstrates that these skills are a critical factor in shaping the academic environment, making them a vital area for training and policy focus. However, it is important to note that there is still a 36.30 percent variation in the attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City that is unexplained by their leadership styles. This suggests that other indicators not explored in the study can also play a significant role. These unaccounted-for variables and indicators offer avenues for future research to explore and could be crucial in forming a more comprehensive understanding of what contributes to the development of strong academic communities.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using a correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of leadership styles in terms of behavior, transformational, and transactional. Moreover, this also identified the extent of attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of leadership styles and the extent of attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public elementary school administrators. Using non-experimental research, the extent of leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120 public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of the Great Man Theory of Carlye (2011) as cited by Jamon (2017) and the Trait Theory of Allport (1939) as cited by Cherry (2016) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of leadership styles in terms of behavior, transformational, and transactional was extensive. Similarly, the extent of attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes was also extensive having obtained a mean of 3.80 which means that it

was sometimes manifested in terms of leadership styles which was also extensive. Hence, the extent of attributes towards an education progression-driven era as demonstrated by public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City was extensive. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and an r^2 value of 0.637 or 63.770 in Table 9 (r -value of 0.765) which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the leadership styles have a significant influence on the attributes of the education progression-driven era of public secondary school heads of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that the regression statistical treatment used in the analysis of the study is useful which means that there is validity in the interpretation of the assumption of the said influences. Finally, indicators of leadership styles such as behavior, transformational, and transactional have a significant influence on attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The leadership styles of public secondary school administrators were extensive. The attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators were also extensive. There was a strong positive correlation between leadership styles and attributes towards the education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators based on the indicators. The overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r -value equal to 0.0.637. This means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the leadership styles and attributes towards the

education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies that an increasing manifestation of leadership styles by the public secondary school administrators of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to an increased manifestation of their attributes towards education progression-driven era. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence on leadership styles on the attributes towards education progression-driven era of public secondary school administrators: Behavior, Transformational, and Transactional.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: Potential school administra-

tors must have proper training on the functions or roles of school administrators before taking the position of school administrator. Teachers must also be aware of the functions of school administrators to fully understand and appreciate the tasks and achievements of their leaders. School leadership empowerment must be given more focus by the Department of Education for it serves as the core foundation of more productive schools. Provide opportunities for school administrators to pursue their professional growth through scholarship programs and human resource development and encourage them to undergo further graduate study. Future Researchers may use the findings as a springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimensions of the study.

5. References

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